

The strategic Human Resource Management- a Talent Management Case of Nonprofit Organizations in Malaysia

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Abstract

Most of the studies on talent management have focused on aspects of talent attraction, talent development, talent succession, talent retention within the corporate world. Very less attention has been paid to determine the effect of these aspects in non-profit organizations by practioners and academia. Knowing the effect of above mentioned areas in non-profit organizations can help non-profit organizations in the area of skill development, career growth, job satisfaction and other related parameters. Thus, the main aim of this study is to find the current practices of talent attraction, talent development, talent succession, talent retention in non-profit organizations which if are present there can help to achieve the work force satisfaction. A qualitative study will be undertaken to explore the perception of talents about the talent management practices in non-profit organizations.

Keywords: Talent management, Talent retention, Ngo's, Talent development, succession, gender, Talent attraction, compensation, Klang Valley, Malaysia

Introduction

The existing practices and ideas of talent management are a response towards a survey released by McKinsey and company by the title of 'The War on Talent'. The survey conducted by this organization displayed the strategic importance of talent management in this aggressive business atmosphere (McKinsey & Company, 2001). Talent can be defined in many ways and one of them is that the employees who are being retained at the cost of others and are offered strategic and important roles in company for future growth and to remain competitive in the market. There is a huge increase in the discussion about talent management in human resource management and development literature (Stahl et al., 2007; Collings et al., 2011). Talent management is a group of ideas and practices utilized in organizations (CIPD, 2011; McDonnell et al., 2010). Talent management mainly refers to attraction, selection, development and managing workforce in a collective and strategic manner (Scullion & Collings, 2011). Many researchers have done work in the area of Talent Management and although there is no consensus between researchers and academia, some of the views about talent management are seen as the proper and close placement of business strategy and work culture of

an organization. These are the main facets of talent management (Farndale et al., 2010; Kim & Scullion, 2011). Even though there is interest in the area of talent management, the output of research is still low in quantity while the idea of talent management is not so new (Burbach & Royle, 2010). The latest works conducted in the field came up with a decision that the lack of proper definition and consensus on talent management has resulted in less understanding and low quantity of research (Mellahi & Collings, 2010; Collings & Scullion, 2009; Lewis & Heckman, 2006). Due to rise in the awareness of talent management implications, more academic research is currently gaining momentum. Since last seventeen years the literature of talent management is gaining momentum and it is currently on the forefront of organizational success and excellence (Gallardo-Gallardo, Dries & González-Cruz 2013). As per the 14th annual survey of PricewaterhouseCoopers (PWC), there is shortage of talent according to the majority of CEOs (66%) and it will hamper the growth of companies. To be sure of success the companies use Talent management to solve their complexities and uncertainties (Nilsson & Ellström, 2012). Talent for various organizations across the spectrum has gained very large strategic importance. The survey conducted by McKinsey has revealed that there are

more than 75 percent of corporate top management is concerned about shortage in talent pool resources. The research by Deloitte has suggested that the main concern of more than 87 percent of human resource managers and directors is retention top talent in an organization. There are various scholars who have suggested a 70:20:10 proportion strategy whereas, 70 percent of development occurs through number of work experiences and activities; 20 percent via relationship building among the team and 10 percent in form of formal developmental courses and activities (Wilson, 2011).

For organizations around the world, talent management of highly efficient and employees with high potential to do well is of increasing strategic importance (Tymon et al., 2010; Vaiman, 2010). The ways to identify the talent and to form a conceptual and theoretical Skelton based on its factors was undertaken by Mäkelä et al (2010). The decision-makers and the elements which affect the path of decisions concerning talent management have received huge importance. The new improvements to talent management have been made by Mäkelä et al (2010) and Mellahi & Collings (2010). These studies have specifically aimed at exploring talent management in corporate world. Little attention has been given to explore the perception of talents themselves and their inclusion in non-profit organization's talent pool. From the perspective of the organization, this is important, because one way to assess the value of a talent program is to explore whether it contributes to the employees', volunteers in organizational commitment and engagement which in turn could increase talent retention within the organization. Along this line some research has explored talent retention strategies which are limited to corporate sector only (Hausknecht et al 2009, Steel et al 2002). However, the area of talent management and its processes suffer from lack of empirical evidence in academic research (Lewis and Heckman 2006). The facts and reasons behind why decision makers act in a certain way have not received much attention from the academia as well as practioners (Mellahi & Collings 2010). Even less research has been aimed at the specific process of forming talent pools especially in non-profit organizations. This study thus aims to minimize this research gap by exploring the perception of talents about the talent

management practices in non-profit organizations. A qualitative study was undertaken to address this problem. Non-profit organizations take part in a vital role in global GDP and its economic potency is extraordinarily apparent. As per The Independent Sector, non-profits add for 5.5% of the gross domestic product for United States of America which is equivalent to 805 billion dollars. John Hopkins University in 2012 displayed a report which showed that the non-profit organizations in 2010 employed 10.7 million people. This is equivalent to 10.1 percent of the overall employees in the United States alone. The John Hopkins University report also points out that non-profit organizations have a certain resistance in economic downturns than that of for-profit organizations. Therefore, the significance of this study will have practical implications. This research will find out the current practices of talent management in non-profit organizations and will enhance the need for talent attraction, retention, development and corresponding practices in nonprofit organizations.

The aim of this study was to find out the current practices of talent management and related parameters having direct influence on the same. This was an exploratory study to discover what is happening in the nonprofit organizations in Klang Valley, Malaysia, which is an area that constitutes the capital city Kuala Lumpur and some surrounding areas. The next section will be composed of literature review, following section will be research methodology, followed by data findings and last but not least will be conclusion.

Previous Research

There are various definitions of talent and talent management but despite these understandings there is lack of consensus on its basic meaning (Lewis & Heckman, 2006) and the precise definition of talent and its management is still somewhat vague (Christensen & Rog, 2008). One of the way for understanding talent and talent management from the perspective of various researchers is have right number of people at the right place at the right time with the right set of skills and level of motivation are basic elements for talent management (Stephenson & Pandit, 2008). One of the way to

define talent may be certain people used by organizations for gaining and maintaining competitive advantage (Collings & Mellahi, 2009; Tarique & Schuler, 2010) and increasing performance of an organization (Nijs et al., 2014). The other way to define talent can be seen as the abilities developed thoroughly in an individual and they utilize these abilities in the activities they adore, discover significant and in what they want to spend their energy. By virtue of it a person can function better in one or more human resource functions. These individuals are better performing than their peers with similar age, experience or education and are more reliable and consistent (Nijs et al., 2014). Talent management is not a modern idea (Patton, 1967), but the research of talent management is inadequate (Burbach & Royle, 2010, Collings & Mellahi, 2009). It is evident that research in this area is insufficient, so it is clear to see that NGO's have been abandoned by researchers of talent management. Similarly, the talent management can be defined in number of ways; one of them is collection of processes that aims to vividly support corporate strategy (Bethke-Langenegger, Mahler & staffelbach, 2011). The chartered institute of personal development (CIPD) describes talent management as premeditated attraction, employment, growth and retention of employees with high potential who are valued by the organization for certain value (CIPD, 2009, p.2). Talent management is considered a tactical instrument to achieve success of an organization (Scullion & Collings, 2011) and to remain competitive in international market (Harris, Craig & Light, 2011). Talent management in an organization clinches to the processes of attracting, developing, retaining the best employees in an appropriate position (Stahl et al., 2007).

Talent Attraction

The attraction of talent in an organization is one of the fundamental countenance in displaying competence and reliable competitive advantage. The core values and the perspective of a potential employee are the key factors which determine the attraction of talent. The function of an organization is a basic point in attraction talent. In other words, we can say that the brand value of an organization will also vastly influence the efforts of talent

attraction. If the perceived brand value of an organization is high the efforts and money spent toward the attraction of talents is less and vice versa. This idea of brand value is supported and believed by many researchers (Iles et al., 2010). The attraction of talents can be viewed in terms external and internal talent and the influx of external talent in an organization is directly proportional to brand value (Glen, 2007). The selection of right talents via ingenious selection requirements offers human resources to attract the eligible and desired people for the required work (Pruis, 2011). As per various scholar and researchers the two key necessities for talent management are attraction and retention of desired workforce (Iles et al., 2010). Thus, the initial phase that talent management practices require is a talent pool, which may comprise of both external and internal talent. Thus, employer brand and employee segmentation are two key things in attraction of talents (Iles et al., 2010). The psychological factor of increased morale when associated with reputed organizations which makes them feel respected and they perceive power to themselves (Glen, 2007). Majority of top organizations around the globe recruit people all the time in search of talent they desire and require. It means that whenever they find a talented person they hire regardless of the need for a new employee or not. This helps these organizations to remain at top and to gain new competitive advantage (chambers et al., 1998).

Talent Development

It is a surprising fact that there is a minute research being done in the area of talent development and the literature which explains the capacity and sets margins of perception (Cohn et al., 2005; Younger & Cleemann, 2010; Cook, 2010). However, it is recognized that talent development speaks as a vital part of talent development (Scullion & Collings, 2011; CIPD, 2011). Thus, for an organization to reach high potential and performance development of talents is required. It is evident that this minuscule research is being conducted in corporate sector and no attention has been paid to nonprofit sector. However, development of talents should be linked with additional learning and development of an employee. Talent development is useful for organizations as well as employee. The

organizations should concentrate on both formal and informal learning for talent development (Areiqat, 2010). Talent development concentrates on the processes of planning, selection and implementation of strategies related to development of whole talent pool within the organization. These processes will help the organization to fulfill its current and future goals. It will also help an organization to meet its talents requirements for future (Garavan, Carbery & Rock, 2012). There are various ways to impart development within the talent pool of an organization. Classic talent development methods like training are vastly effective at inducing various skills with the employees inside and organization workplace (Lahti, 1999; Hirsh, 2009). The talent development within an organization focuses on the needs of an organization with utmost priority (Pruis, 2011).

Succession

The talent succession is a vital practice that saves time, money and effort for the search of talent outside the organization. Succession also enhances the repercussion of reengineering and at the same time it helps to maintain the diverse talent pool within an organization (Wolfe, 1996). Succession of talent in various organizations has different definitions as per needs and strategies. Therefore, the organizations can practice talent management as per their needs (Hor et al., 2010). The question that will arise in near future for management is concern of society and lack of availability of internal talent within organizations (Rothwell, 2010). The main aim for the practices of succession is developing and modeling of leadership in an organization (Hor et al., 2010). The policy of an organization to secure its future in terms of leadership requirements will lead to growth and maintaining competitive edge in the market (Hills, 2009). One of the elements for lack of leadership options available in organizations is less concentration on succession. Organizations consider the succession as separate thing from talent management and it takes responsibility away talent managers (Groves, 2007). There are five vital policies that help in proper succession and its planning. Leadership assessment using 3C's, talent planning, mixed development, mentoring/coaching and having a vision about succession (Hills, 2009). Succession of talent is key ingredient to keep the

organizational culture alive and take it forward (Rothwell, 2010).

Talent Retention

In the world of fierce competition retention of workforce has become a vital strategic characteristic for organizations. Retention of talented employee has the same importance as attracting the same. This will help organizations to achieve their short and long-term objectives (Mehta, Kurbetti, & Dhankhar, 2014). The factors which influence the retention of workforce in the opinion of employees are career progression, independence in work place, experience etc. All of these factors uplift the morale of employees and help and organization to align their talent management practice in line with employee retention (Kroon & Freese 2013). There are more than twenty-four factors which influence the talent retention. Some of them are work culture, compensation, work life balance etc (Mehta, Kurbetti, & Dhankhar, 2014). The one vital reason for employees to stay in the current organizations is succession (Bagga, 2013). Talent management and retention practices of successful organizations are vital factor to uphold their superiority and leadership in the market. Retention of employees is factor which leads to customer satisfaction and loyalty in service sector (Devi, 2009).

Compensation

There are number of factors which take away an employee from the current workplace and of the main element for that is dissatisfaction with compensation and benefits (Bhatnagar, 2007). Thus, for improved talent management practices organizations must pay competitive salary, good working conditions, cooperative teams etc. (Devi, 2009). The scholars from various varieties of areas have debated for long over the issue of compensation and its effect. They have studied the behavior of top management in this regard (summarized in Finkelstein, Hambrick & Cannella, 2009). The various studies have suggested that the salary of an employee affects the performance of an employee and in context the performance of an organization (Devers et al., 2008). Pay scale is an important factor in talent management and practices for an organization. It helps an organization to retain and grow its talent internally. The payment or compensation can have variety of methods to

distribute it. Some of them are pay for job, pay for person, pay for skill etc (Shields et al., 2015).

Global Talent Management

Global talent management is becoming an area of attention for academia as well as practitioners. The area of global talent management is still in its infancy yet, it has caught the eye of many over past decades (Collings, 2011). Global talent management and its strategic objectives have been discovered in recent past (Scullion, Collings, & Caligiuri, 2010; Stahl et al., 2012; Tarique & Schuler, 2010). The mobility of international employees is key factor in the success of mega corporations and organizations (McDonnell, Lamare, Gunnigle, & Lavelle, 2010; Sparrow, 2007; Stahl et al., 2012). The practice of global talent management is more focused on employees possessing high potential, performance or with high degree of human capital through the organization (Stahl et al., 2012). Across the global major organizations are in a continuous battle for the quality and quantity of talent to boost their operations and other functions in an organization (Farndale, Scullion, & Sparrow, 2010; Hartmann, Fiesel, & Schober, 2010). The global talent management is having various phases and it starts with identification of positions of significant importance, then identification of talent pool and issuing the suitable position for the selected candidates (Mellahi & Collings, 2010). There are various studies suggesting that the workforce with global or international experience have capacity for completion of assignments with greater efficiency in comparison to those with only local experience (Mäkelä, 2007).

Gender and Talent Management

The existing Talent management debate highlights the significance of background considerations (Minbaeva & Collings, 2013; Sparrow et al., 2014). It is being noticed that the freedom of work is discriminative between male and females even in western countries. There is a stigma attached to female gender in workplace (Hewlett & Rashid, 2010). The cultural values and undeveloped social security of various places presents itself as hindrance especially for females in taking up a career path which is more social and independent (Schinnenburg & Adam, 2013). One of the standards of competition is job performance, ability

and contribution lead to better career succession. The other system is growth of ideas and seen as an elite talent helps them to be better and progress organizations objectives (Ng et al., 2005). The various studies came with the notion that female talent goes unnoticed in comparison to males of same organization which respect to these systems in place (Cabrera, 2009). One of key elements for this gender bias comes from role stereotype which is placed in favour of male career positioning (Schinnenburg et al., 2014). Industrial revolution has play a vital role in this bias, whereas, males have been given the role to be public and productive in contrast to females as secretive and reproductive. This stereotyping has made way for sexism and career is seen synonym with male thing (Schneidhofer et al., 2010). The study by Heilman gives a picture that value of female career and their performance in organizations in devalued (Heilman, 2001). The gender bias is in favour of males and they are being selected in organization even if they are less qualified in competition with a female colleague (Vance & McNulty, 2014). In some Asian culture the presence of strong role descriptions the bias is more as compared to in west. These cultural things help male of society feel superior to the female counterparts (Vance & McNulty, 2014). The day to day experiences and developmental work in an organization shapes the behavior patterns. It also develops the identity of workforce in particular industry for example, the reducing number of female in engineering (Nelson & Irwin, 2014). From last two decade's a noticeable difference has emerged, there is a huge gap in demand and supply of talents in majority of organizations especially in developed countries markets (Stahl et al., 2007).

Research Method

This paper has channeled its focus towards what is really happening in the organizations within the Klang valley. The qualitative approach was used to uncover the practices of Talent management in Klang valley Malaysia. The top management of these nonprofit organizations were the respondents of this research. The empirical data was collected from the unstructured interviews organized with the top management of six nonprofit organizations in Klang valley. The interview protocol was used to collect the data from respondents. The interview protocol consisted of the items which were helpful

to determine the practice of Talent Management in nonprofit organizations. The correctness of information planned to be incorporated during the research has significant importance for the validity and reliability of the research undertaken (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill 2009).

Data Analysis

The initial stage was of data analysis was compilation of data by transcription of interviews in chronological manner. The second step is division of data as per various themes generated and more importantly as per the objectives of research. The third step is reassembling of data as per objectives of study as well as certain common themes in the data set. The next is of interpretation where in the researcher has decoded the comments by various NGO's. At the end there has to be conclusion. It provided the overview of data collected in a glance

The concept of Talent Management by NGOs

NGO1 believes that the talent management is acquiring, developing and retaining highly skilled employees and on the same way of perception the main step in talent management is how we approach the talent and develop a mutual connection with them and minimizing the communication gap is notion of talent management for NGO2. NGO5 is also thinking on same lines as they believe that the accesses to elite human resource talent pool that will help them gain competitive advantage and fulfill the organizational needs. They believe that talent management will help their organization to enhance its brand value and on those lines, have better financial position to achieve the organizational goals. NGO6 is of the belief that talent management is about development of talent so that they can create a team of best talent available to achieve organizational goals. They also consider talent management as a science that will help them to attract and recruit the talent they desire and require to full their short term and long-term goals. While as, NGO3 believes that talent management is about to know employee of an organization. On top of knowing their employees NGO4 think it is obliged to understand the attitude and needs of their workforce. From the above discussion's the author can determine that these organizations have some vague or generic idea

about talent management but as the author has also discussed the other vital parameters of talent management, which helps to get a clearer picture. The author had taken these parameters and organization in an organized manner. First of all, the author has discussed about the talent attraction in these organizations. NGO1 is responsive in their recruiting process. While they do not have any strict guidelines for hiring the organization maintains industry wide standard for the same. Along the same line in NGO2 their organization maintains industry wide standards while hiring employees. The organization has a mixture of reactive and proactive policy for hiring. It depends on the financial position of organization as well as upcoming projects. They also believe that the majority of NGO's do not have any standard operating procedure but they have developed over the time and hire employees accordingly. NGO5 is an organization that has some specific guidelines to attract and hire new talent available in the talent pool. They believe that whoever is inducted in the organization is more of a family rather than employees. They hire talent for both short and long terms durations depending on projects and employees. So, there is no particular time or need when they hire. NGO6 has standard policies in recruiting but with certain shifts coming to industry and the nature of its disruption. They often take the path of creative approach standard while recruiting. On the contrary NGO2 they do not have any set of guidelines or industry wide standards for recruiting. They only hire people when they need them for a specific period of time. But they like to see the commitment of people before hiring, even after they join them. This is an important parameter for the organization. Along the same lines NGO3 at the moment does not have any standard policy for recruiting but they have some criteria for the same. By virtue of these criteria's they try to attract right kind of people to work for their organization. The organization has a responsive policy while hiring i.e. they hire only on need basis. At the moment, they do not follow the industry wide standards while looking for potential employees from the existing talent pool. The second parameter was about to see the understanding of talent management and to discuss what these organizations believe about development. From

NGO1 the author found out that the development of employees in their organization is considered as an important aspect for them. They provide not only the professional development but personal development as well. While believing that development of employees is best for both parties involved. NGO2 believes that the development of employees is important for both employer and employee. They let the employees know that there are trainings happening at various locations and let them apply for themselves. As they are still in their initial phases of growth they do not offer financial support for the training and development courses. In NGO3 they offer training and development programs for their employees. They highly recommend and prioritize new employees in their organization for training and development courses and programs. They believe that development of employees is an important practice. They try to make their employees an all-rounder. They try to provide new skills so that employees can act in a multi-functional role and emerge as leaders. They believe that the training and development is equally important for an organization as it is for employees. Motivation is one of the key challenges to keep employees at same passion of working with them as same as when they started. They try to develop common vision and mission for a particular project so that employees feel more of responsibility rather than just working for money. The NGO5 believes that the development of their workforce is an important aspect for their organization as they provide training to everyone at the organization from time to time for skill development and to realign them to their vision and mission. In the case of NGO 4 and 6 they think talent development for them is an Invest in the right people and they can automate their operations for a long time. They provide training and development courses to their employees if needed by them. The next parameter to evaluate is the understanding of talent management by these organizations is talent retention. NGO2 believes that they do not think that employee retention is an important practice because if their employees get a better opportunity elsewhere they should go and develop themselves and later on if want to rejoin them they are welcome. NGO3 thinks retention of employees is not a useful practice. They believe you cannot make

people stay and work for you when they want to leave for one reason or other. They do not pay any attention to retention of employees. On contrary NGO 4, 5 and 6 value the retention of talent. They believe that the employee retention is a very useful practice in their organizations. Retention of employees is always beneficial to the organization as it enhances the roles and skills of the members of the organization and develops organizations. They try to keep their employees close as in this industry it is very important to have employees for long durations of time. This helps these organizations to keep focus of their real job which is to help the society. While as these two group of organizations have opposing notions about the talent retention the organization number is neutral about the retention of its employees. The organization does not put effort in this practice. While having neutral view about retention of talent in the organization but they like taking time out to and listen to their employees is an important core value for them.

Valuing Talent Management in the Workplace

The term value has different value for many people at personal level but at organizational level there are some common values or organizational values for them. In this discussion's the author has explored the value of talent management in the nonprofit organizations the author interviewed. NGO1 believes that talent management is every organization's investments. They also think that the talent management is beneficial for an organization if they know how to do it properly. Otherwise, developed employees will venture for better opportunities outside. NGO 2 and 3 on the same lines believe that Talent management is a very important scope that NGO's have to look into. They need to appreciate and look into the real perspective of talent management. It is a very important practice so that they can know their employees so that they can do right work for them. Talent management practices should be a standard in every kind of industry and organization, so that they can get better results on current and future projects and assignments. NGO5 thinks that talent management streamlines and clarifies the needs and goals of an organization and this is essential for success. They believe that talent management is important in this competitive world as well as it surely improves the

performance and enhances the goals and vision of an organization. NGO6 has notion that talent management will definitely improve their organization. Talent management is helpful for both employee and employer and can generate a good data about the new trends in the market. NGO 4 has somewhat different ideas about talent management when compared to above mentioned organizations. They believe that it may help the organization but they are not sure as it is under developed area and needs to develop more research and practioners. They also think talent management is not yet too reliable and it needs to get more mature. The value of talent management can also be determined indirectly by measurement of other parameters like compensation of workforce and global talent management. The findings about the compensation of talent are discussed under the heading of valuing talent management in workplace. The reason for this is the talented workforce will continue working for you if only they receive what they deserve. So if the organizations fail to do that the talent will leave them and indirectly the author has said that they do not care about the talent management practices. NGO1 does offer regular bonuses and increments for the talented employees, but at the same time they do not maintain industry wide standards of compensation. NGO2 along the same lines only provide an accepted amount of salary to their employees besides that there is no other type of compensation for their employees. They do not have enough provisions to have industry wide standards of compensation. Similarly, NGO 3 and 5 believes that the main thing in compensation is that they provide experience other than salary which is more important than monetary benefits. They believe that the experiences they offer while an employee is in their workforce are very unique and help the employees to improve their quality of live by its virtue. They offer a decent salary to their employees. They also mentioned that NGO's face financial problems and they are unable to offer bonuses and other perks to them. They do not follow the industry wide standards in terms of compensation. While NGO 4 and 6 have different practices in the area of compensation at the same time these organizations have some of exciting ways to compensate their employees. Some of them are stock options, bonuses, flexible work-hours and

extended holidays for newlyweds and parents etc. They also compensate their employees by offering monetary gifts to them during their respective festive seasons. They also have annual performance appraisal for their employees. There is a rating system for that in these organizations. It provides competitiveness within these organizations as well as with competing NGO's as well. They believe that compensation in nonprofit industry should be very competitive so that more people are attracted toward this work. These organizations have industry wide standards for compensation as they think it is an important practice. The second parameter the author has measured in this arena of valuing talent is also discussed. The importance of this parameter is that due vast and brisk developments in the world, we are forming a global village. Due to various agreements between various countries boundaries are becoming irrelevant. The mobility of talent is greater than ever before. Many young talents are migrating in search of better opportunities and this trend is on rise. This mega trend has helped majority of organization for example, Apple as its CEO Steve Jobs was a son of a migrant. So, this trend cannot and should not be neglected. The organizations that were interviewed had similar beliefs about the global talent management. All of them were on the same pattern of thinking, as they believed that diverse workforce make their organizations more efficient and a desires workplace. They believed that it is a necessary practice to gain competitive edge over competing organizations as well as to gain different perspective about various issues. These organizations are keen on implementing the global talent management practices but due to various reasons they cannot do the desired. The common problems faced by these organizations in this regard are language barrier, cultural barriers and more importantly the tedious and unreliable immigration policies and practices. Therefore, they are unable to implement global talent management.

Gender and Talent Management

The talent pool available at present is scares; it cannot fulfill the needs of organization across the globe. The talent can be any one regardless of their gender as already discussed in the literature review. There are various patriarchal practices in developed

as well as developing countries. These obsolete ideologies are creating various issues for females in workplace. The author went to discover the ideas about gender and talent management in various organizations. To the author's surprise the findings were astonishing and on head on with what rest of world believes and does. These nonprofit organizations are open minded as well as just in their practices related to gender. All of these nonprofit organizations believe that talent does not depend on the gender of a person. The author found out that these organizations do not indulge in any kind of sexism. While most of the top management interviewed were females themselves. It also displays the validity of these statements related to gender and talent management. While all of these organizations categorically declined any involvement in gender bias in their respective organizations but NGO4 prefer female staff because of their dedication and NGO6 have some issues in succession of females in the hierarchy. These findings are unique and exemplary. The Malaysian nonprofit organizations should be role model for various organizations across the world especially Muslim world in the gender and talent management related practices.

Talent Management as a Viable Practice

Talent management is the need of hour for all organizations including nonprofit organizations around the world. The practice of talent management provides solutions current human resources issues with better results. There are various elements that compose the talent management and its practices. In order to make talent management successful and viable in nonprofit organizations they should implement it in gradual manner. The first and most important practice which nonprofit organizations should implement is talent attraction. Many organizations have proved that talent management is an important practice in this competitive world. The talent attraction will help the whole sector of nonprofits as attraction will make this area a lucrative career option. The nonprofit sector will grow and the rest of phases can be gradually implemented which are not already present there. The response for validity and usability of talent management by all of these NGO's was in favour of it. These nonprofit organizations believe that talent management is way

to go for all of industry. They believed that it is vital for them to gain competitive advantage. They believe that talent management will help them in automation of their operations. Talent management for them is also a necessary tool for them to stay afloat and live in future as per the general consensus among these organizations. These organizations believe that there is huge need for talent in nonprofits organizations across the globe as humanitarian vows are increasing day by day. They think the Government in Malaysia should take an active part in the funding of nonprofit organizations so that they can survive and implement talent management practices in their respective organizations. These organizations believe that the talent management is a viable practice for nonprofits sector.

Discussion

As the author discovered the current practices of talent management in various nonprofit organizations in Klang Valley and the author has reached to a conclusion that there is some vague idea about talent management within these organizations. This study was an expletory research in the area of talent management in nonprofit organizations situated in Klang Valley Malaysia. The author went on a journey to find out the notions and practices of talent management in various nonprofit organizations. Some of the parameters to find out the practices of talent management were talent attraction, talent development, talent retention, compensation, global talent management and gender and talent management. The author found out that the nonprofits organizations in klang valley have some vague idea about talent and talent management. The author found out that the top management of these organizations also realizes the importance of talent management practices in their respective organizations. As the literature review guide's, us through this process and shows us that talent attraction is the initial phase in the implementation of talent management practices in an organization. The author came to find out that these organizations have no or minimal attention and practice towards the attraction of talents. Talent development is considered as vital and beneficial practices for employee as well as employer by these nonprofit organizations. These organizations lay

great emphasis toward the talent development practices. Each of these organizations has developed a unique strategy for the developmental process of employees. In the aspect of talent retention there are variety of opinions and practices in each of these organizations. Therefore, the author has said that there is consensus and proper knowledge about that importance of talent retention in respective organizations. These nonprofit organizations were not too keen to share the details of salary packages and other monetary and non-monetary benefits they offer to their employees. These organizations also believe that the international employee can help them to achieve their target with greater efficiency but the language barrier along with the unreliable immigration department were the main obstacle to hire international employees. These organizations believe that anyone can have the desired set of skills they require regardless of their gender. So, they do not indulge in the gender based discrimination in any of human resource or talent management elements. After conducting this brief study, the author believes that there is still lot of uncharted territory in the field of talent management especially in the perspective of nonprofit organizations. This study opens the door to this area and there is scope of various findings and improvements which will have practical as well as theoretical implications.

Conclusion

As the author came across various nonprofit organizations in Klang valley, many facts and practices of these organizations in regards of talent management was discovered. It is clear that there is a basic idea of talent management in these organizations, but at the same time it is also clear that they do not have any academic or proper knowledge from a course or a workshop, rather it is general perspective and common-sense ideas regarding talent management. After going through long interviews and discussion with various top management personnel of these organization, the author has suggested few changes and improvements in current practices. Some of the suggestions based on through review of previous work done in the area of talent management. The top management of nonprofit organizations should

first of all get the proper overview of talent management and its various aspects. So, the author recommends that they should attend talent management courses and workshops. The key element for any process is its initiation. Here the author saw that there is no attraction, which is supposedly to be its initial phase. The author recommended that these nonprofits hire an external consultant for the policy development of talent attraction. This can be helpful for all of organizations as they are recruiting talent from grassroots level and it will be more economical for them to start these practices. As in the area of talent development, these organizations have respectable level of talent development practices. The author has recommended that these organizations should have a fixed time in year for training and development of their employees. Most of these organizations do not believe in talent retention. The author has also suggested that they should practices certain level of retention for best employees. Otherwise due high employee turnover the organizations can be manipulated and suffer economic loss. So, retention policies need to be developed in these organizations. Compensation is one of the key factors which influence both employee and employer. The author has discovered that due to below standard compensations in majority of nonprofit organizations is a common practice. The author would like to recommend here that the compensation should be adequate or if the organization is going through economic difficulties they can offer them non-monetary benefits, which can be equally beneficial for employees as well the organization. As we know that the world is becoming a global village and boundaries are becoming more and more irrelevant. There are many cooperation zones evolving such as European union (EU), Association of South East Asian Nations(ASEAN), Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa (BRICS), Group of Twenty (G20) etc. we need to recognize the importance of recruiting international employees to get perspectives of how the culture of those particular countries work. As the author came across these NGO's they do not prefer to employ foreign talent even if they are more qualified and experienced. This is mainly due to the immigration laws of Malaysia, which are obsolete and hamper the practices of global talent

management. This has created a problem for local organization as well as the economy of the country. The author has suggested that various organizations should come together and form a union and take a legal route to abolish the current practices of immigration in the country. The other reason the author found out in the way of global talent management is language barrier. The author suggests that organizations should make it compulsory for their employees to be efficient in English and communicate in English at the workplace. This will help the organization as well as employee. Organization will be able start ventures in developed countries and employees will be more employable. This will also help Malaysia to grow in terms of investment and business startups. More and more people from rest of the world will come to Malaysia for business as they did in Singapore. All of the organizations mentioned that they do not have gender bias practice. This is the bright side of the various organizations for treating both the genders equally. So, the author has recommended them to keep doing what they are doing in terms of gender related issues.

Acknowledgement

I acknowledge that This work was partially supported by Ministry of Higher Education Malaysia (Kementerian Pendidikan Tinggi) under Research Initiative Grant Scheme (RIGS) number RIGS 16-357-0521.

References

- i. Areiqat, A. Y., Abdelhadi, T., & Al-Tarawneh, H. A. (2010). Talent management as a strategic practice of human resources management to improve human performance. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 2(2), 329-341
- ii. Axelrod, E. L., Handfield-Jones, H., & Welsh, T. A. (2001). War for talent, part two. *The McKinsey Quarterly*, 9-9.
- iii. Bagga, G. (2013). How to keep the talent you have got. *Human resource management international digest*, 21(1), 3-4.

- iv. Bethke-Langenegger, P., Mahler, P., & Staffelbach, B. (2011). Effectiveness of talent management strategies. *European Journal of International Management*, 5(5), 524-539.
- v. Bhatnagar, J. (2007). Talent management strategy of employee engagement in Indian ITES employees: key to retention. *Employee relations*, 29(6), 640-663
- vi. Burbach, R. and Royle, T. (2010), "Talent on demand? Talent management in the German and Irish subsidiaries of a US multinational corporation", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 39 No. 4, pp. 414-31.
- vii. Cabrera, E. F. (2009). Fixing the leaky pipeline: Five ways to retain female talent. *People and Strategy*, 32(1), 40.
- viii. CHAMBERS, C. (1998). liii } i.
- ix. Christensen Hughes, J., & Rog, E. (2008). Talent management: A strategy for improving employee recruitment, retention and engagement within hospitality organizations. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 20(7), 743-757.
- x. CIPD (2009), "Employer branding: maintaining momentum in a recession", *Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD) Guide*, CIPD, London
- xi. CIPD (2011), *Shaping the Future – Sustainable Organization Performance*, Final Report, CIPD, London.
- xii. Cohn, J. M., Khurana, R., & Reeves, L. (2005). Growing talent as if your business depended on it. *Harvard business review*, 83(10), 62.
- xiii. Collings, D.G. and Mellahi, K. (2009), "Strategic talent management: a review and research agenda", *Human Resource Management Review*, Vol. 19 No. 4, pp. 304-313.
- xiv. Collings, D. G., Scullion, H., & Dowling, P. J. (2009). Global staffing: A review and thematic research agenda. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20: 1251–1269.

- xv. Collings, D.G., Scullion, H. and Vaiman, V. (2011), "European perspectives on talent management", *European Journal of International Management*, Vol. 5, pp. 453-462.
- xvi. Cook, S. (2010). Talent management: Key questions for learning and development. *Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal*, 24(4).
- xvii. Devi, V. (2009). Employee engagement is a two-way street. *Human resource management international digest*, 17(2), 3-4.
- xviii. Devers, C. E., Cannella Jr, A. A., Reilly, G. P., & Yoder, M. E. (2007). Executive compensation: A multidisciplinary review of recent developments. *Journal of management*, 33(6), 1016-1072.
- xix. Farndale, E., Scullion, H., & Sparrow, P. (2010). The role of the corporate HR function in global talent management. *Journal of World Business*, 45: 161–168.
- xx. Finkelstein, S., Hambrick, D. C., & Cannella, A. A. (2009). *Strategic leadership: Theory and research on executives, top management teams, and boards*. Oxford University Press, USA
- xxi. Gallardo-Gallardo, E., Dries, N., & González-Cruz, T. F. (2013). What is the meaning of 'talent' in the world of work?. *Human Resource Management Review*, 23(4), 290-300.
- xxii. Garavan, T. N., Carbery, R., & Rock, A. (2012). Mapping talent development: definition, scope and architecture. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 36(1), 5-24.
- xxiii. Glen, C. (2007). Fostering talent opportunity: getting past first-base. *Strategic Direction*, 23(10), 3-5.
- xxiv. Groves, K. S. (2007). Integrating leadership development and succession planning best practices. *Journal of management development*, 26(3), 239-260.
- xxv. Harris, J. G., Craig, E., & Light, D. A. (2011). Talent and analytics: new approaches, higher ROI. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 32(6), 4-13.
- xxvi. Hartmann, E., Feisel, E., & Schober, H. (2010). Talent management of western MNCs in China: Balancing global integration and local responsiveness. *Journal of World Business*, 45: 169–178.
- xxvii. Hausknecht, J. P., Rodda, J. M., & Howard, M. J. (2009). Targeted employee retention: Performance-based and job-related differences in reported reasons for staying. *Human Resource Management*, 48, 269-288. Retrieved [insert date], from Cornell University, ILR School site: <http://digitalcommons.ilr.cornell.edu/articles/140>
- xxviii. Heilman, M. E. (2001). Description and prescription: How gender stereotypes prevent women's ascent up the organizational ladder. *Journal of social issues*, 57(4), 657-674.
- xxix. Hewlett, S. A., & Rashid, R. (2010). India's crown jewels: female talent. *Harvard Business Review Blog Network*, 3.
- xxx. Hills, A. (2009). Succession planning—or smart talent management?. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 41(1), 3-8.
- xxxi. Hirsh, W. (2009). *Talent management: Practical issues in Implementation*. Institute for Employment Studies
- xxxii. Hor, F. C., Huang, L. C., Shih, H. S., Lee, Y. H., & Lee, E. S. (2010). Establishing talent management for company's succession planning through analytic network process: Application to an MNC semiconductor company in Taiwan. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 60(3), 528-540.
- xxxiii. Iles P., Chuai, X., & Preece, D. (2010) *Talent Management and HRM in Multinational companies in Beijing: Definitions, differences and drivers*. *Journal of World Business* 45: 179–189.
- xxxiv. Kim, C.K. and Scullion, H. (2011), "Exploring the links between corporate social responsibility and global talent management: a comparative study of the

- UK and Korea”, *European Journal of International Management*, Vol. 5 No. 5.
- xxxv. Lahti, R. K. (1999). Identifying and integrating individual level and organizational level core competencies. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 14, 59–75
- xxxvi. Lewis, R.E. and Heckman, R.J. (2006), “Talent management: a critical review”, *Human Resource Management Review*, Vol. 16 No. 2, pp. 139-154.
- xxxvii. Mäkelä, K. (2007). Knowledge sharing through expatriate relationships: A social capital perspective. *International Studies of Management & Organization*, 37(3), 108-125
- xxxviii. McDonnell, A., Lamare, R., Gunnigle, P., & Lavelle, J. (2010). Developing tomorrow’s leaders—Evidence of global talent management in multinational enterprises. *Journal of World Business*, 45: 150–160.
- xxxix. Mellahi, K. and Collings, D.G. (2010), “The barriers to effective global talent management: the example of corporate élites in MNEs”, *Journal of World Business*, Vol. 45 No. 2, pp. 143-149.
- xl. Mehta, M., Kurbetti, A., & Dhankhar, R. (2014). Review Paper—Study on Employee Retention and Commitment. *International journal of advance research in computer science and management studies*, 154(5).
- xli. Minbaeva, D., & Collings, D. G. (2013). Seven myths of global talent management. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24: 1762–1776.
- xlii. Nelson, A. J., & Irwin, J. (2014). “Defining what we do—all over again”: Occupational identity, technological change, and the librarian/Internet-search relationship. *Academy of Management Journal*, 57(3), 892-928.
- xliii. Ng, E. S., & Burke, R. J. (2005). Person–organization fit and the war for talent: does diversity management make a difference?. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 16(7), 1195-1210.
- xliv. Nijs, S., Gallardo-Gallardo, E., Dries, N. & Sels, L. (2014) A multidisciplinary review into the definition, operationalization and measurement of talent. *Journal of World Business*, 49 (2): 180-191
- xlv. Nilsson, S., & Ellström, P. E. (2012). Employability and talent management: challenges for HRD practices. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 36(1), 26-45.
- xlvi. Pruis, E. (2011). The five key principles for talent development. *Industrial and commercial training*, 43(4), 206-216.
- xlvii. Rothwell, W. J. (2010). Effective succession planning: Ensuring leadership continuity and building talent from within. AMACOM Div American Mgmt Assn.
- xlviii. Saunders, M., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A., & Wilson, J. (2009). *Business research methods*. Financial Times, Prentice Hall: London.
- xlix. Schneidhofer, T. M., Schiffinger, M., & Mayrhofer, W. (2010). Mind the (gender) gap. Gender, gender role types, and their effects on objective career success over time. *Management Revue*, 437-457.
- i. Schinnenburg, H., Boehmer, N., Walk, M., & Handy, F. (2014). Young talent: individualistic, boundaryless and disloyal? Challenges for international HRM and development. In Conference paper presented at the 13th Conference of International Human Resource Management, Kracow, June (Vol. 27).
- ii. Schinnenburg, H., & Adam, S. (2013). Warum Mütter sich (nicht) für Führungspositionen entscheiden. In *Wirtschaftliche Implikationen des demografischen Wandels* (pp. 349-363). Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.
- lii. Scullion, H. & Collings, D.G. (2011) (eds.) *Global Talent Management*, Routledge, London.

- liii. Shields, J., Brown, M., Kaine, S., Dolle-Samuel, C., North-Samardzic, A., McLean, P., & Plimmer, G. (2015). *Managing Employee Performance & Reward: Concepts, Practices, Strategies*. Cambridge University Press
- liv. Sparrow, P. R. (2007). Globalization of HR at function level: Four UK-based case studies of the international recruitment and selection process. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 18: 845–867
- lv. Sparrow, P., Scullion, H., & Tarique, I. (Eds.). (2014). *Strategic talent management: Contemporary issues in international context*. Cambridge University Press
- lvi. Stahl, G. K., Björkman, I., Farndale, E., Morris, S. S., Paauwe, J., Stiles, P., ... & Wright, P. M. (2007). Global talent management: How leading multinationals build and sustain their talent pipeline. INSEAD faculty and research working papers, 24.
- lvii. Stahl, G., Björkman, I., Farndale, E., Morris, S. S., Paauwe, J., Stiles, P., & Wright, P. (2012). Six principles of effective global talent management. *Sloan Management Review*, 53(2), 25-42.
- lviii. Steel, R.P., Griffeth, R.W., & Hom, P.W. (2002). Practical retention policy for the practical manager. *Academy of Management Executive*, 16, 149-162.
- lix. Stephenson, E., & Pandit, A. (2008). *How companies act on global trends: A McKinsey global survey*. Boston: McKinsey.
- lx. Tarique, I., & Schuler, R. S. (2010). Global talent management: Literature review, integrative framework, and suggestions for further research. *Journal of world business*, 45(2), 122-133.
- lxi. Tymon, W.G., Strumpf, S.A. and Doh, J.P. (2010), “Exploring talent management in India: the neglected role of intrinsic rewards”, *Journal of World Business*, Vol. 45 No. 2.
- lxii. Vaiman, V. (2010), “Managing talent of non-traditional knowledge workers – opportunities, challenges, and trends”, in Vaiman, V. (Ed.), *Talent Management of Knowledge Employees: Embracing Non-traditional Workforce*, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, pp. 1-22.
- lxiii. Vance, C. M., & McNulty, Y. (2014). Why and how women and men acquire global career experience: A study of American expatriates in Europe. *International Studies of Management & Organization*, 44(2), 34-54
- lxiv. Wilson, W. J. (2011). *When work disappears: The world of the new urban poor*. Vintage.
- lxv. Wolfe, R. (1996). *Systematic succession planning building leadership from within*. Crisp Learning
- lxvi. Younger, J., & Cleemann, C. (2010). Growing your HR brand. *Strategic HR Review*, 9(4), 177-184.